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Developing quantitative Adverse Outcome Pathways: An ordinary differential equation-based computational framework

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ABSTRACT

The Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) biological framework was introduced in 2012, yet defining a mathematical/computational framework for quantitative AOP (qAOP) development remains an open problem. In order to properly unravel the intricate biological mechanisms described by AOPs and provide quantitative predictions to support risk assessment, a computational model should provide a clear time-course prediction of key events (KEs), as well as describe the key event relationships (KERs) linking a molecular initiating event (MIE) to an adverse outcome (AO). Ultimately, the mathematical description of those links entails the possibility of quantitatively predicting adverse effects based on early events.

Here, we propose an ordinary differential equation (ODE) - based qAOP framework, as ODEs provide a time-course description of KEs and KERs. We illustrate how the application of computational techniques, such as Bayesian inference and Leave-one-out cross-validation (LOO-CV), can assist AOP development, introducing concepts of qAOP model selection and qAOP updating. Furthermore, we compare ODE and response–response based qAOP models, showing that ODE-based qAOPs can avoid erroneous predictions potentially resulting from response–response qAOPs. Finally, we show how ODE parameter variability can be linked to AO variability across a population. Overall, this framework serves as a valuable mathematical and computational tool for the development of qAOP models, enhancing our comprehension of intricate biological pathways associated with adverse outcomes.

1. Introduction

The Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) framework is a conceptual construct for the study of biological systems with application in toxicology, and aiming to support hazard and/or risk assessment of chemicals [1]. An AOP provides a qualitative description of how a ‘molecular initiating event’ (MIE) ultimately leads to an ‘adverse outcome’ (AO) through triggering of multiple sequential ‘key events’ (KEs), that are defined as perturbations of the biological system at the (sub)cellular or tissue level [2]. Such perturbations are in principle measurable, e.g., by next-generation sequencing to monitor changes in gene expression compared to the physiological situation. Note however that finding a suitable measurement technique is not always straightforward. The MIE usually involves the interaction of a chemical with a biomolecule, also referred to as molecular target [3]. This initiates a cascade of KEs that is considered to be sequential in the AOP concept. The relationship between two subsequent KEs is referred to as a key event relationship (KER). The cascade of KEs ultimately links the MIE to the AO, which refers to adverse effects at the individual, population or ecosystem level [4].

One of the advantages of the AOP framework lies in its flexibility when it comes to the level of detail in the description of a biological system [5], integrating information spanning from molecular to organ level and linking mechanistic details to apical end points. Moreover, AOPs can be updated when new information arises. For instance, a single AOP represents a simple situation in which only a single MIE is triggered and the sequential cascade of KEs ends in a single AO. However, one could consider multiple AOPs having one or more KEs in common: those AOPs can be combined to form a more complicated AOP network [6]. An AOP network is indeed a more complicated construct than a single AOP, and it involves typically multiple MIEs and AOs and highlight how these interact via common KEs.

Whereas a qualitative AOP entails the description of a biological system, with consequent application in toxicology, hazard identification [7] and chemical testing strategies [1]; a quantitative AOP (qAOP) is a model, built upon a qualitative AOP [8], which aims to mathematically describe the KERs. Successful quantification of (parts of) an AOP in general provides further confidence in the AOP, yet qAOP

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models also support regulatory decision-making by providing quantitative predictions of outcomes based on early events [9]. Specifically, qAOP models are useful to infer compound exposure levels required to trigger an AO [10], predict effects of other chemicals with similar mode of action [11] and perform in vitro to in vivo extrapolation [12]. This range of applications highlight the relevance of qAOPs both from scientific and ethical perspectives, as their employment could be useful in reducing animal testing [13].

Several mathematical frameworks can be employed in KER descriptions, including Bayesian networks, ordinary differential equations (ODEs) and dose–response based models [14]. The modeling framework selection highly depends on the desired output, as well as the available data. Here, we introduce a mathematical framework for qAOP modeling that explicitly takes into account the temporal dynamics of KE triggering while avoiding the level of detail required for systems biology models. To this purpose, we propose to employ ODEs that consider KEs as the system’s variables, i.e., as central players. This approach allows a straightforward mathematical description of KERs, as well as the inclusion of additional elements such as feedback loops within and between KEs. Such feedback loops play an important role in determining the actual strength of biological responses, i.e., the responses that an AOP aims to capture within KEs. For instance, it has been shown that chemical disruption of thyroid hormone (TH) signaling can be properly modeled with several feedbacks [15,16]. Other relevant examples of feedback loops can be found in several neurodegeneration-related AOPs entailing AOs such as Parkinsonian motor deficits [17] and impairment of learning and memory in adults [18]. Omitting such biological processes when quantifying KERs might lead to missing relevant information and, eventually, not being able to properly predict AOs. Another main advantage of an ODE-based qAOP framework is that it delivers a clear time-course depiction of KEs, which implies a deep understanding of the involved biological processes.

One of the strengths of the proposed ODE-based qAOP framework lies in the level of detail that can be reached in describing response variability amongst the population. Indeed, despite exposure to equivalent doses of a particular compound, individuals may manifest diverse levels of adverse effects. We show how ODE parameter variability can be linked to an AO distribution within a population, explaining potentially large differences between population subgroups. Moreover, we compare our ODE-based qAOP framework to response–response models that are often employed for qAOP modeling. We show how one can derive response–response curves from ODE solutions, for any time point within the considered time-frame of the model. Thus, simple response–response models are contained within every ODE-based qAOP.

2. Methods

We first introduce all the mathematical systems employed in the Results section. We refer to [19] for general theory on ODEs, dynamical systems and bifurcation theory.

2.1. Generic qAOP formulation

In order to quantify qAOPs, we employ the following generic ODE system, which describes a simple AOP:

$$\begin{cases} MIE = MIE(t), \\ \frac{dKE_1}{dt} = KER_1(MIE, KE_1), \\ \frac{dKE_i}{dt} = KER_i(KE_{i-1}, KE_i), \text{ for } i = 2, \dots, n-1, \\ \frac{dKE_n}{dt} = KER_n(KE_{n-1}, KE_n). \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The variables KE_i , $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ represent the activation strength of key event i , for each KE belonging to the AOP. Thus, we consider quantification of all KERs in an AOP, although data limitations may not allow for such full quantification. Similarly, the MIE variable corresponds to the activation strength of the MIE over time. In system (1) we implement this as an explicit time-dependent function, but in principle one could utilize an ODE equation to describe its dynamic. Such function includes parameters that incorporate the dependence on dose level and the rate of MIE decay.

System (1) is the simplest case of an ODE-based qAOP. In this sequential cascade, each KER only depends on the corresponding KE and the upstream KE. Note that the dependence of a KER on the corresponding KE is not explicitly shown in the AOP scheme. However, it makes biological sense to consider the rate of change of a biological pathway to depend on the pathway itself, since its elements inherently interact with one another.

As an extension of the simplest AOP, we can consider two sequential AOPs that intersect. Following the qAOP formulation employed in system (1), the two separate qAOPs take the following form:

$$\begin{cases} MIE_1 = MIE_1(t), \\ \frac{dKE_1}{dt} = KER_1(MIE_1, KE_1), \\ \frac{dKE_2}{dt} = KER_2(KE_1, KE_2), \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

and

$$\begin{cases} MIE_2 = MIE_2(t), \\ \frac{dKE_3}{dt} = KER_4(MIE_2, KE_3), \\ \frac{dKE_2}{dt} = KER_5(KE_3, KE_2). \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In the AOP network for these combined AOPs, KE_2 depends on both KE_1 and KE_3 , thus to describe the network the equation for KE_2 should be updated to:

$$\begin{cases} MIE_1 = MIE_1(t), \\ MIE_2 = MIE_2(t), \\ \frac{dKE_1}{dt} = KER_1(MIE_1, KE_1), \\ \frac{dKE_3}{dt} = KER_4(MIE_2, KE_3), \\ \frac{dKE_2}{dt} = KER_{upd}(\overline{KER}_2(KE_1, KE_2), \overline{KER}_5(KE_3, KE_2)), \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

where \overline{KER}_2 and \overline{KER}_5 have the same mathematical formulation as KER_2 and KER_5 , but different parameter values. Specifically, in the Results section we will show an example on how such update can be implemented. We will then consider the following qAOP systems:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dMIE_1}{dt} = -\tau_1 MIE_1, \\ \frac{dKE_1}{dt} = MIE_1 - d_1 KE_1, \\ \frac{dKE_2}{dt} = \frac{k_{12} KE_1}{h_{12} + KE_1} - d_2 KE_2, \\ MIE_1(0) = S_1, KE_1(0) = KE_2(0) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dMIE_2}{dt} = -\tau_2 MIE_2, \\ \frac{dKE_3}{dt} = MIE_2 - d_3 KE_3, \\ \frac{dKE_2}{dt} = k_{32} KE_3 - d_2 KE_2, \\ MIE_2(0) = S_2, KE_3(0) = KE_2(0) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where τ_i is the decay rate of MIE_i , d_i is the decay rate of KE_i , k_{ij} is the (maximal) activation rate of KE_i induced by KE_j , h_{ij} is the level of KE_i at which its induction by KE_j is half-maximal, and S_i is the initial value for MIE_i . The additive qAOP network is then defined by:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dMIE_1}{dt} = -\tau_1 MIE_1, \\ \frac{dMIE_2}{dt} = -\tau_2 MIE_2, \\ \frac{dKE_1}{dt} = MIE_1 - d_1 KE_1, \\ \frac{dKE_3}{dt} = MIE_2 - d_3 KE_3, \\ \frac{dKE_2}{dt} = \alpha \frac{k_{12} KE_1}{h_{12} + KE_1} + (1 - \alpha) k_{32} KE_3 - d_2 KE_2, \\ MIE_1(0) = S_1, MIE_2(0) = S_2, KE_1(0) = KE_2(0) = KE_3(0) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

with $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ representing the relative weight by which KE_1 contributes to activation of KE_2 .

2.2. Feedback qAOP

As biological pathways are typically intertwined with many feedback mechanisms within and across pathways, achieving congruence of qAOP temporal responses with experimental-based quantifications of KEs will likely require such feedbacks within the qAOP. For example, to include a feedback from the second KE to the first KE the generic ODE-based qAOP from system (1) becomes:

$$\begin{cases} MIE_1 = MIE_1(t), \\ \frac{dKE_1}{dt} = KER_1(MIE_1, KE_1, KE_2), \\ \frac{dKE_2}{dt} = KER_2(KE_1, KE_2). \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Note that the logic in the KER formulation presented in system (1) is preserved. The only difference with system (1) is that in system (8) KE_1 is also a function of KE_2 , due to the (positive) feedback loop from KE_2 to KE_1 . As a specific instance of such a feedback qAOP, in the Results section we consider:

$$\begin{cases} MIE(t) = ke^{-\tau t}, \\ \frac{dKE_1}{dt} = -d_1 KE_1 + MIE \cdot KE_2 + \epsilon, \\ \frac{dKE_2}{dt} = -d_2 KE_2 + s_2 \frac{KE_1^m}{k_1^m + KE_1^m} + \epsilon. \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

For simplicity, in system (9) we consider the MIE to be a linear function of the dose parameter (that we define as k). Note that in practice one will consider a limited range within which k varies, such that the MIE formulation makes biological sense. We also let the MIE decay in time, reflecting clearance processes that typically occur in vivo or in vitro settings. Clearly, other MIE formulations should be utilized in different biological situations. Furthermore, ϵ is the rate of external stress, which in this case is the same for both KEs. This results in an equilibrium level of KE activation in the absence of chemical exposure. With respect to the relations between MIE and KEs, we consider KER_1 to be a linear function of MIE . Alternatively, one could employ a Hill function or Michaelis–Menten type of equation [20] to describe the influence of MIE on KE_1 . In this example we employ such a Hill function to describe the positive effect of KE_1 on KE_2 [21] (where m represents the Hill exponent).

2.3. qAOP calibration and selection

When there is uncertainty on which biological processes should be included in a qAOP, one can consider different qAOP variants, compare how well they describe a data set, and subsequently perform model selection. In order to illustrate this possibility of qAOP model selection in the Results section, we define three similar qAOPs, with qAOP A being the following ODE system:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dMIE}{dt} = -\tau MIE, \\ \frac{dKE_1}{dt} = \epsilon + MIE - d_1 KE_1, \\ \frac{dKE_2}{dt} = -d_2 KE_2 + k_{12} KE_1 + k_2 MIE, \\ MIE(0) = S_0, KE_1(0) = KE_2(0) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Similarly, we define as qAOP B the following ODE system:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dMIE}{dt} = -\tau MIE, \\ \frac{dKE_1}{dt} = \epsilon + MIE - d_1 KE_1, \\ \frac{dKE_2}{dt} = -d_2 KE_2 + k_{12} KE_1, \\ MIE(0) = S_0, KE_1(0) = KE_2(0) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

The difference between systems (10) and (11) lies in the term $k_2 MIE$, i.e. an additional KER from MIE to KE_2 .

Lastly, we consider qAOP C to be:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dMIE}{dt} = -\tau MIE, \\ \frac{dKE_1}{dt} = \epsilon + MIE - d_1 KE_1, \\ \frac{dKE_2}{dt} = -d_2 KE_2 + k_{12} KE_1 + \frac{k_2}{h_2 + MIE}, \\ MIE(0) = S_0, KE_1(0) = KE_2(0) = 0, \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where we consider an inhibitory KER from MIE to KE_2 .

To achieve model selection, each of the model variants need to be ‘calibrated’ to the same experimental data set containing KE dynamic data (i.e. measurements of KEs at multiple time points) to the qAOP model. We performed this by using the CmdStanR package, which is the R interface for CmdStan [22]. CmdStan is the shell interface to Stan [23], a probabilistic programming language providing Bayesian inference for model calibration, including ODEs, through Markov chain Monte Carlo methods. Three Stan files are defined, one for each model. Those files consist of different blocks: in the ‘functions’ block we define the ODE model, including the state variables, equations and parameters. In the ‘data’ and ‘parameters’ block, we define the input quantities and the quantities to be inferred, respectively. The ‘transformed parameters’ block is employed to run and store the solution of the ODE system. In the ‘model’ block, priors to the inferred parameters and likelihood functions are defined. The likelihood function uses both input data and the output of the ‘transformed parameters’ block and quantifies how likely the observed data are given a particular set of parameter values. Finally, the ‘generated quantities’ block is employed for model selection using the Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation (LOO) criteria [24].

2.4. Response–response modeling

A generic qAOP response–response model takes the following form:

$$\begin{cases} KE_1 = f_1(Dose), \\ KE_2 = f_2(KE_1), \\ \dots \\ KE_n = f_n(KE_{n-1}). \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

In system (13), we do not take the time course of KEs into account. Rather, a single time point is utilized and all the KERs are defined based on KE measurements taken on the same time point. Note though that in principle one could consider the response–response relations of subsequent KEs at diverging time points, for example, when the expectation is that an early response of KE_n has a late effect on KE_{n+1} . For this reason, such time point information is requested in the AOP-Wiki in the subsection ‘time scale’ within the topic ‘Quantitative understanding’.

In the Results section, we present an example in which we generate a response–response model starting from artificial data generated with an ODE system. The ODE system we consider is the following:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dMIE}{dt} = -\tau MIE, \\ \frac{dKE_1}{dt} = -d_1 KE_1 + \frac{MIE}{h_1 + MIE}, \\ \frac{dKE_2}{dt} = -d_2 KE_2 + \frac{k_{12} KE_1^n}{h_{12} + KE_1^n} + \frac{i_{MIE}}{h_2 + MIE}, \\ MIE(0) = S_0, KE_1(0) = 0, KE_2(0) = KE_{20}. \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

In order to generate the dose–response curves, we consider the time-varying solutions of system (14) in which we let S_0 vary in a defined range. We then only select the solutions at the specific time-points we consider.

2.5. AO formulation and AO score

To translate the set of KEs into an expected AO, we consider variability in KERs amongst individuals in a population to be the main source for variability at AO level. Let us consider a generic qAOP with n parameters that all (indirectly) affect the probability of an AO. We refer to the parameter space as S_p , with $S_p \subset \mathbb{R}_+^n$ (i.e., we consider all parameters to be positive because they represent biological processes).

To describe the severity of the AO, it comes natural to define the AO score as $AOs \in [0, 1]$. If $AOs = 0$, the AO does not take place at all; if $AOs = 1$, we have the most severe grade of the AO. Although we interpret this AO score in a continuous manner, in practice this may need to be discretized depending on how an AO can be quantified within a population. For instance, in the case of acute kidney injury (AKI), according to the RIFLE criteria [25] there are five different classes of AO related to the glomerular filtration rate and urine output criteria: Risk, Injury, Failure, Loss and End-stage kidney disease. Taking into account the AKI example, one could make the following classification:

- $AOs \in [0, 1/6]$: no adverse outcome;
- $AOs \in [1/6, 2/6]$: risk;
- $AOs \in [2/6, 3/6]$: injury;
- $AOs \in [3/6, 4/6]$: failure;
- $AOs \in [4/6, 5/6]$: loss;
- $AOs \in [5/6, 1]$: end-stage kidney disease.

The AO score, coherently with the AOP structure, depends on the last KEs downstream whose nodes are directly linked to the AO through KERs (we will refer to these as *final KEs downstream*). Note that earlier KEs also indirectly affect the AO, acting through the final KEs. Let us first consider the case of having only have one KE directly linked to the AO, we will then generalize the mathematical formulation for the case of multiple KEs.

Having defined the space of parameters S_p , we can identify which combination of parameters leads to the highest value of the final KE in steady state (or, more generally, at a given time point). Let T_{max} be the maximum time of simulation. We then scale the AO score with the maximal value that can be achieved within the parameter space, which is $\max_{S_p} f(KE_{last}|_{t=T_{max}})$ (with KE_{last} being the final KE downstream in an AOP). For a specific choice of parameters in S_p (i.e., vector $\bar{p} \in S_p$) the AO score is then calculated with the following function:

$$AOs : S_p \longrightarrow [0, 1]$$

such that

$$AOs(\bar{p}) := \frac{f(KE_{last}|_{t=T_{max}, \bar{p} \in S_p})}{\max_{S_p} \left\{ f(KE_{last}|_{t=T_{max}}) \right\}}, \quad (15)$$

where f is a C^1 function describing the final KER in a response–response manner. Note that we hereby consider the last KE to directly relate to the AO considering the behavior at a fixed time point. Note that if time-course data on the AO is available, one could formulate an ODE equation for the AO as well, to then consider the AO solution at a given time point, similarly to Eq. (15). In this case, AO is an ODE solution, and one would have:

$$AOs(\bar{p}) := \frac{AO|_{t=T_{max}, \bar{p} \in S_p}}{\max_{S_p} \left\{ AO|_{t=T_{max}} \right\}}. \quad (16)$$

In the case where two or more final KEs downstream drive the AO, one can consider the weighted sum of those KEs to affect the AO score, where the weights are determined based on the biological relevance of each KE in order for the AO to take place. Let us suppose to have m final KEs downstream (i.e., KE_1, \dots, KE_m) and let $\{w_1, \dots, w_m\}$ be the weights associated to them. We further require $\sum_{i=1}^m w_i = 1$ and $0 \leq w_i \leq 1$ for all $i = 1, \dots, m$. Similarly to (15), we then define the AO score as

$$AOs(\bar{p}) := \frac{\sum_{i=1}^m w_i f_i(KE_{i}|_{t=T_{max}, \bar{p} \in S_p})}{\max_{S_p} \left(\sum_{i=1}^m w_i f_i(KE_{i}|_{t=T_{max}}) \right)}, \quad (17)$$

where the functions f_i are defined in a similar manner as in the case of Eq. (15).

3. Results

3.1. A dynamic qAOP framework with feedback loops

Our envisioned qAOP framework should include the dynamics of MIE, KEs and AO upon exposure to chemicals, and should allow for threshold-like KERs. To model this in a natural way, we opted for an ordinary differential equation (ODE)-based formalism (see system (1) in the Methods). This also enables one to include feedback loops within the qAOP framework (see system (8) in the Methods), which are widespread in biological systems. Even though the AOP framework was originally designed to only include sequential KERs, feedback loops are now formally included within the AOP concept [26], as explained in the AOP developers handbook (see [27]). Therefore, it is important to provide a qAOP framework where feedback loops are properly implemented, which ODEs effectively allow for.

As a generic example, we define an AOP that involves two KEs that connect the MIE to the AO in a sequential manner. However, we also consider an additional KER from KE_2 to KE_1 , which represents a positive feedback (Fig. 1A). We then formulate this as a qAOP ODE model (see ‘‘Feedback qAOP’’ in the Methods; system (9)). Note that we implemented the positive feedback as a single mathematical term that controls both the rate at which the MIE triggers KE_1 and the positive feedback from KE_2 to KE_1 .

The positive feedback in this specific qAOP leads to a saddle–node bifurcation in the system, which can be observed when comparing responses to low and high doses that trigger the MIE. Therefore, we perform a bifurcation analysis with respect to the dose parameter k , and consider the response of the final key event downstream (KE_2) (Fig. 1B). Indeed, the system is characterized by two stable branches (stable nodes; red lines) and one unstable branch (saddle; blue line) [28]. This implies that for low dosing a very low KE_2 response is expected in the long run, whereas for high dosing the KE_2 response suddenly becomes very high (Fig. 1C) (9). Moreover, such bistability entails that subpopulations amongst a population of individuals that are exposed to

Fig. 1. Including feedback loops into an ODE-based qAOP model can explain the variability in outcome among a population. (A) Schematic representation of AOP including feedback loop. (B) Bifurcation diagram related to the dose parameter k . (C–D) Time-course plots of KE2 dynamics for different values of k (C) and d_1 (D). Default parameter values: $d_1 = 1$, $s_2 = 4$, $d_2 = 1$, $\epsilon = 0.2$, $m = 3$, $k_1 = 1$, $k = 0.4$. The varied parameters, for both k and d_1 , are chosen in a range of values between 0 and 2 incrementing by 0.1. Values are presented in arbitrary units (a.u.).

chemicals in a similar manner (i.e., have similar MIE triggering) may have very different outcomes. For instance, individuals likely differ in parameters such as the decay rate of KE_1 because they will differentially express certain enzymes. To demonstrate this phenomenon, we fix the dose parameter and vary the KE_1 degradation rate (d_1) (Fig. 1D). This variability results from the changes in the steady state values of KE_2 as dependent on the parameter d_1 (see system (9)). In conclusion, taking an ODE modeling approach as a qAOP framework allows for a natural inclusion of feedback loops that can lead to bifurcations. Such bifurcations can explain how large difference in response can result from minor changes in either exposure or parameter variability across patients.

3.2. qAOP model calibration and selection

In order to test whether a developed AOP is quantitatively consistent with experimental measurements on MIE, KEs and/or AO, one needs to calibrate qAOP model parameters to those data. This typically means considering multiple qAOP implementations, i.e., with different mathematical terms per KER, because it is not a priori known whether, and in what way a KER depends on a specific KE. We refer to this process as qAOP selection, and we illustrate this here with a simple AOP where we compare two possible KERs for the link of KE_1 to KE_2 . Specifically, we consider this KER_2 to either depend on both the MIE and KE_1 (top panel in Fig. 2A, corresponding to qAOP A (system (10)) in the Methods), or on KE_2 only (middle panel in Fig. 2A, corresponding to qAOP B (system (11)) in the Methods). We first created artificial time course data on KEs considering qAOP B as underlying ‘truth’. We then calibrated model parameters for both qAOP A and B to these artificial data (Fig. 2B), compared the input parameter values with calibrated parameters, and studied the goodness-of-fit visually (for convergence of the fits see Supplementary Fig. 1). As expected, the LOO estimate prefers qAOP B over qAOP A, which is evident from the higher expected log pointwise predictive density ($elpd_{loo}$) and lower Leave-One-Out Information Criterion (loo_{ic}) (Table 1). Given that qAOP B is also the simplest model one would thus select this qAOP as representative for the data at hand, providing a clear argument for disregarding the KER from KE_1 to KE_2 . Thus, this example shows how a model selection approach can provide information on the biology of an AOP.

Table 1

Leave-One-Out method output for calibrating either qAOP A or qAOP B to qAOP B - based artificial data.

	Estimate qAOP A	SE qAOP A	Estimate qAOP B	SE qAOP B
$elpd_{loo}$	25.41	11.14	28.21	9.59
p_{loo}	3.14	1.38	1.78	0.58
loo_{ic}	-50.81	22.29	-56.43	19.17

Table 2

Leave-One-Out method output for calibrating either qAOP A or qAOP B to qAOP A - based artificial data.

	Estimate qAOP A	SE qAOP A	Estimate qAOP B	SE qAOP B
$elpd_{loo}$	22.02	12.09	27.10	6.58
p_{loo}	10.01	4.60	6.99	2.28
loo_{ic}	-44.03	24.18	-54.21	13.15

We next generated artificial data using qAOP A as underlying truth and repeated the same procedure as before (Supplementary Fig. 2; convergence of the fit shown in Supplementary Fig. 3). In this case, the LOO method still prefers qAOP B over qAOP A, even though we generated artificial data using qAOP A (Table 2). This implies that adding an additional KER from KE_1 to KE_2 does not help in describing the trend of the KE_2 data.

To show a final example in which a more complicated model is preferred over a simpler one, we generated artificial data considering qAOP C as underlying truth and repeated the same procedure as before. Thus, we calibrated both qAOP B and C to artificial data generated with qAOP C as underlying truth and compared the out-of-sample model performance employing the LOO method (Fig. 2C, Supplementary Fig. 4 shows convergence of fit). In this case, the LOO method strongly prefers the more complicated model qAOP C over the simpler qAOP B (Table 3). This is because qAOP B cannot describe the dynamics of KE_2 as well as qAOP C, i.e. the inhibition of KE_2 by the MIE qualitatively changes the dynamic behavior. Notice that, in this last example, we generated more artificial data points to better show the inhibition effect from MIE to KE_2 .

These simple examples showcase that the presented qAOP model selection procedure offers an approach to deliver simplified (q)AOPs

Fig. 2. qAOP model calibration and selection. (A) AOP A, B and C schemes. AOP A and C consist of an additional KER compared to AOP B. (B) Model fit for qAOPs A (left column) and B (right column), using artificial data generated from model qAOP B. Model parameters to generate artificial data: $\tau = 0.05$, $k_1 = 0.2$, $d_1 = 0.5$, $k_{12} = 0.3$, $d_2 = 0.4$. (C) Model fit for qAOPs B (left column) and C (right column), using artificial data from model qAOP C. Model parameters to generate artificial data: $\tau = 0.05$, $k_1 = 0.2$, $d_1 = 0.5$, $k_{12} = 0.3$, $d_2 = 0.4$, $k_2 = 0.2$, $h_2 = 0.3$. The artificial data in (B) and (C) was generated either for 10 (B) or for 20 (C) time points. For each time point, 5 different measurements were generated by adding random noise to the ODE system solution. The random noise was normally distributed with mean 0 and SD either 0.1 (B) or 0.3 (C). Values are presented in arbitrary units (a.u.).

Table 3
Leave-One-Out method output for calibrating either qAOP B or qAOP C to qAOP C - based artificial data.

	Estimate qAOP B	SE qAOP B	Estimate qAOP C	SE qAOP C
$elpd_{loo}$	-1.05	6.34	8.35	4.02
p_{loo}	8.05	3.38	4.94	1.79
loO_{ic}	2.10	12.69	-16.71	8.04

whenever the relations between KEs are sufficiently straightforward. Thus, even if there is convincing biological evidence that a specific KER takes place, a simplified quantitative model may describe the data well and, in this sense, provide the desired AO estimation via a simplification of the qAOP. Moreover, in some cases we can computationally infer the underlying biology of the corresponding AOP, by demonstrating that certain KERs are needed to properly describe data.

3.3. qAOP updating

In the AOP framework, individual AOPs are considered to be living documents [29]. This means that if a new AOP is defined and that model shares at least one common KE with a previously developed AOP, those two AOPs can be combined into an adverse outcome network (AON). An example of such *AOP updating* is shown in Fig. 3A. Importantly, although the combination of AOPs into a network is

straightforward from a qualitative perspective, the related qAOP can be modified as well and this is less straightforward. We refer to this process as qAOP updating.

Consider for example the theoretical case where two sequential AOPs converge on the same KE (KE_2), which implies that the involved KERs might affect each other. Mathematically this means that the separate qAOPs (system (2)) and (system (3)) need to be updated such that the new KER (KER_{upd} , defined as in system (4)) depends on KER_2 and KER_5 , as defined in models (2) and (3), respectively. All the remaining KERs remain the same as in the original models, therefore the only mathematical challenge in the qAOP updating process is to define KER_{upd} . In general, one only needs to define updated KERs related to the ODEs defining the dynamic of KEs that are shared by the original AOPs.

To demonstrate how this works in our ODE-based framework, we propose an example of two qAOPs, defined by systems (5) and (6). Those qAOPs can be joined and updated to system (7), which could potentially improve the description of the common KE (i.e. KE_2 in our example), and thus ultimately of the AO. However, alternatively the dynamics of the common KE might already be well described by each of the simple qAOPs (5) and (6), in which case one would not need to consider the more complicated network to have a proper prediction on that specific KE and ultimately the AO. To demonstrate this, we generated artificial data from the updated network in system (7) and we calibrate these data to the separate qAOPs (5) and (6).

Table 4

Leave-One-Out method output for calibrating either $qAOP_{up}$ or $qAOP_{down}$ to qAOP network-based artificial data. Related to results in Fig. 3B–E.

	Estimate $qAOP_{up}$	SE $qAOP_{up}$	Estimate $qAOP_{down}$	SE $qAOP_{down}$
$elpd_{loo}$	96.71	3.37	93.11	6.48
p_{loo}	2.97	0.96	2.53	1.23
loo_{ic}	-193.42	6.74	-186.23	12.97

Table 5

Leave-One-Out method output for calibrating either $qAOP_{up}$ or $qAOP_{down}$ to qAOP network-based artificial data. Related to results in Supplementary Fig. 5.

	Estimate $qAOP_{up}$	SE $qAOP_{up}$	Estimate $qAOP_{down}$	SE $qAOP_{down}$
$elpd_{loo}$	70.50	12.83	9.27	37.14
p_{loo}	9.27	4.36	11.16	4.12
loo_{ic}	-141.01	25.66	-18.54	74.27

In this example, both $qAOP_{up}$ (Fig. 3B–C; system (5)) and $qAOP_{down}$ (Fig. 3D–E); system (6) described the artificial data reasonably well, although the re-estimated parameters related to the non-updated KERs were somewhat off compared to those used to generate the artificial data (vertical red lines in Fig. 3C and 3E).

Contrary to the above example, one of the two simple qAOPs might be insufficient to describe the common KE data, in which case considering a more complicated model of the full AON would be necessary. To show this, we again generated artificial data with system (7), choosing different parameter values and calibrated the separate qAOPs (5) and (6) to those data. In this case, model (6) does not accurately predict KE_2 data (Supplementary Fig. 5B). Specifically, with this different parameter choice KE_2 does not exhibit a sustained dynamic as in the previous example, but it decays in time. With a constant MIE 2 over time and, as a consequence, KE_3 sustained, the linear KER 5 cannot explain the decay of KE_2 in time. Thus, one would need to consider KER 2 to properly calibrate the model.

As expected, a LOO-based analysis confirms that in this case the more complicated qAOP describes the data much better than the simpler qAOP (Tables 4 and 5). Specifically, $qAOP_{down}$ has higher SE values for $elpd_{loo}$, p_{loo} and loo_{ic} compared to $qAOP_{up}$. In conclusion, the presented qAOP updating by means of calibrating various qAOPs to data can support AOP extension or simplification.

3.4. Comparison between ODE and response–response approach

A frequently used alternative to ODE modeling as a qAOP framework is ‘response–response modeling’, in which mathematical equations (see system (13)) are sought that properly describe the quantitative relation between KEs (and between the applied dose and the first KE, called ‘dose–response’), usually at single time points. We here compare the results of such a response–response approach with those of an ODE-based approach. We introduce model (14), an ODE-based qAOP involving two KEs (Fig. 4A). This model example involves three KERs; KER 1 and 2 link the MIE to KE_1 and KE_2 , respectively. While KER 1 entails a positive effect of MIE to KE_1 , KE_2 is inhibited by the MIE.

Since the MIE is a decaying function of time (Fig. 4B), the response–response relationship between the two KEs might differ at time points for which the MIE has different levels of activation. To investigate this, we selected three different time-points and, for each one of those, we generated dose–response curves for each KE (Fig. 4C). Despite a qualitative similarity between the different dose–response curves for each KE, the quantitative behavior clearly differed. We then plotted the response–response relationship of KE_2 as function of KE_1 (Fig. 4D). Not only the quantitative, but also the qualitative behavior of the response–response curves was highly dependent on the considered time point. Thus, with the ODE-based approach we can deduct a larger amount of information on the considered AOP than with a response–response

approach, which is likely to also affect AO prediction. Importantly, employment of an ODE-based qAOP development allows to recover the response–response relationships between KEs for any time point within the simulated time domain.

3.5. Mathematical description of adverse outcome distributions

In order to arrive at an AO prediction with our suggested ODE-based qAOP, one would ideally like to obtain an ‘AO distribution’, i.e., a distribution of AO quantifications scaled within a specific range, e.g., between 0 (full absence of AO) and 1 (full-fledged AO). This range could then be compared to patient (or animal) data that have been exposed to a compound of study, e.g. histological quantifications of tissue damage, for which discretization of the AO distribution might be necessary (as exemplified in the Methods).

One option to generate an expected AO distribution is to again link the patient variability to the variability in the ODE parameters that we considered before. Thus, we consider a subset in the parameter space to represent a subset of patients in the total population. Here, different subsets of the parameter space correspond to different groups of patients, sharing common characteristics (e.g. the rate at which the MIE affects a KE, or the rate of change of a KE as dependent on the previous KE). The simplest way to make this link mathematically is to consider the model predictions for the final KE preceding the AO as directly reflecting the AO. To translate the model prediction for the final KE for a particular parameter combination to a continuous AO score between 0 and 1, we divide the obtained value with the maximum possible value for the final KE (see Eq. (15)). Note that the values for the final KE might first need transformation to accommodate non-linear relations between this KE and AO. In case multiple KEs are known to jointly affect the AO in an AOP network, the weighted sum of this set of final KEs can be used instead (see Eq. (17)).

We illustrate the procedure to arrive at an AO distribution with our earlier example, in which a positive feedback within the qAOP leads to a saddle–node bifurcation (Fig. 1; Eq. (9)). Such distribution can be defined by running our qAOP model for all the possible combination of parameter values varying in the space of parameters. Namely, in the case of system (9), one wants to solve the system $\forall \bar{p} \in S_p$, and then calculate and store the AO for each iteration. For illustrative purpose, we fixed τ , k_1 and m and let the rest of the parameters vary. Moreover, to show how the AO distribution depends on the dose, we performed the simulation for five different values of k (with $k = 1$ considered as the highest dose value).

For $k = 0.5$, we obtained a left-skewed distribution, which means that the AO score is low for the majority of the population (Fig. 5A). The bistability of the system (see bifurcation diagram in Fig. 1B), became evident for $k = 0.625$ and $k = 0.75$, for which we obtained bimodal distributions (Fig. 5B–C). For relatively high values of k ($k = 0.875$ and $k = 1$), we obtained a normal distribution centered to high AO score values (Fig. 5D–E). In order to show how our mathematical formulation of the AO can be translated to a response–response analysis, we set a threshold value for the AO score in between the two observed peaks and quantified the percentage of AO score observations above the threshold for different values of k (Fig. 5F). This is a further evidence of how one can derive a dose–response relationship linking exposure to AOs in a population from an ODE-based qAOP. In conclusion, our ODE-based qAOP framework provides an AO prediction which can be directly linked to patient variability.

4. Discussion

In this study, we introduced a mathematical framework for qAOP development based on ODEs. The choice of ODEs lies in the possibility of properly representing the expected chronological sequence of KE activation, while taking advantage of a natural description of interactions between entities that vary over time (i.e., KEs). Indeed, having a clear

Fig. 3. Updating of KERs in the ODE-based qAOP modeling framework. (A) Schematic representation of the AOP updating process. (B, D) Fit with either model qAOP_{up} (B) or model qAOP_{down} for KE₁ and KE₂ (blue lines) to artificial data generated with system (7) (black dots — mean; black error bars — SD). The artificial data was generated for 17 time points using the following parameter values: $\tau_1 = 0.05$, $\tau_2 = 0$, $d_1 = 0.05$, $d_3 = 0.06$, $\alpha = 0.8$, $k_{32} = 0.08$, $k_{12} = 0.07$, $h_{12} = 5$, $d_2 = 0.1$, $S_1 = 0.1$, $S_2 = 0.05$, $KE_n(0) = 0$. For each time point, 5 different measurements were generated by adding random noise (normally distributed with mean 0 and SD 0.05) to the ODE system solution. (C, E) Posterior distribution of the parameters for qAOP_{up} (C) or qAOP_{down} (E). The red lines correspond to the parameter values chosen to generate artificial data for the parameters involved in the non-updated KERs. Values are presented in arbitrary units (a.u.). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

picture of the evolution of the system in time is relevant to understand and predict the biological cascade represented by an AOP. Namely, we do not just want to analyze the cause and effect relationship between two KEs.

An additional advantage of an ODE-based approach for qAOP development is given by the possibility of considering the natural variability of MIE, KE and AO responses within a population of patients subject to the same type of exposure. Unraveling the causes of such variability in response to exposure is a key element in risk assessment [30]. Employing ODE models can partially help in understanding and predicting such susceptibility differences. Specifically, we showed how the variability between patients can be modeled as variability in the parameters of the ODE. The presence of bifurcations in the underlying ODE system can lead to bistability in the system (e.g., Fig. 1B) [31], which provides a potential explanation for vastly different responses

between individuals. This is because the existence of two or more stable states of a certain KE for the same input signal (MIE) implies that there is a threshold level for the input signal to be crossed in order to activate the next KE. As the exact threshold will depend on the exact KERs per individual (i.e., the model parameters for a unique individual), this implies that for some individuals the ‘personal’ threshold is crossed whereas this is not the case for others. This can partially explain the large variability in AO responses across individuals. Moreover, it is possible to implicitly include additional variables into our framework which are not compound-specific but can be determinants for the AO assessment. For instance, old age, obesity and the presence of additional diseases are risk factors for AKI [32]. The parameter variability in ODEs can be associated with the variability in such additional factors, that then determine the details of the thresholds within the system and, therefore, different outcomes. As an example in the context of

Fig. 4. ODE-based qAOP models provide a wider amount of information compared to response–response models. (A) AOP scheme. (B) Time-course dynamic of the solution of the ODE system, including MIE, KE₁ and KE₂. (C) Dose–response curves for KE₁ and KE₂ at time-points 10, 30 and 50. (D) response–response curves of KE₂ as function of KE₁ at time-points 10, 30 and 50. In (B–D), we used system (14) for simulation with parameter values: $\tau=0.1$, $h_1=5$, $d_1=0.1$, $k_{12}=0.3$, $h_{12}=10$, $i_{MIE}=0.9$, $h_2=2$, $d_2=0.3$, $S_0=1$, $KE_{20}=2$. Values are presented in arbitrary units (a.u.).

Fig. 5. The ODE-based qAOP framework provides an AO prediction over a population of patients. (A–E) AO score distribution corresponding to $k=0.5$ (A), $k=0.625$ (B), $k=0.75$ (C), $k=0.875$ (D), and $k=1$ (E). We sampled parameters from normal distributions, namely $d_1 \sim N(1,0.1)$, $\epsilon \sim N(0.2,0.01)$, $d_2 \sim N(1,0.1)$ and $s_2 \sim N(4,0.3)$. (F) Percentage of AO score values above a threshold of 0.3 plotted as function of k .

a physiologically-based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) model (rather than qAOP), the age-dependent glomerular filtration rate (GFR) can affect the plasma concentration of chemicals, thereby affecting AO risk [33].

In order to have a proper alignment with the AOP framework, we proposed the concept of *qAOP updating* within our qAOP framework. Importantly, it is common in the AOP framework to have AOP networks in constant update once new AOPs, sharing common KEs with other pre-existing AOPs, are published. Examples of such AOP networks are present in the literature, e.g. related to lung damage [34–36], neurotoxicity [37,38] and hepatotoxicity [39]. With respect to the case of thyroid-mediated developmental neurotoxicity, AOPs 42 [40], 134 [41], 8 [42], 54 [43], 12 [44] and 13 [45] share common KEs that can be combined to form an AOP network (as in Fig. 3A). Our mathematical framework provides a straightforward solution to tackle the updating process, i.e., by redefining the mathematical terms representing KERs. Moreover, we showed how model selection methods (e.g. Akaike information criterion, LOO) can be performed in order to assess which model better describes a data set [46]. Importantly, this can give biological insights on which KERs are more relevant than others, which provides guidance to modify the related AOP scheme, which could in some cases imply AOP extension and in other cases AOP simplification. This makes our qAOP framework not only a mathematical construct per se, but also an effective tool to investigate the biology described by AOPs.

Although we here advocate an ODE-based framework for qAOP development, choosing this as mathematical framework is not always the most appropriate choice. Indeed, the mathematical framework selection strongly depends on the quantitative AOP data that are available: for instance, it is challenging to properly calibrate ODE models with KE data recorded at a single time point. In that regard, alternative modeling approaches have been used for qAOP development (e.g. response–response, Bayesian networks) [14,47,48], which are less data hungry for model parameter calibration. However, we showed that such alternative model formalisms to implement a qAOP may lead to erroneous results, which could be catastrophic for risk assessment. Specifically, we investigated various examples of hypothetical qAOP systems to underline the difference with response–response modeling. We demonstrated that response–response modeling is not always accurate in KE prediction and can be highly dependent on the selected time point. ODEs entail the full time course description of MIE and KEs, eliminating the single time point bias of the classical response–response approach. Because from an ODE system one can derive response–response relationships between KEs for each single time point, our ODE-based qAOP approach can be viewed as an extension of response–response modeling rather than as an alternative. As an example, for AOP 25 in the AOP-Wiki [49], the quantitative description of response–response relations is partially based on ODE models considered to be at steady state (see Connolly et al. [9]).

In our work, we considered the case where dynamic quantified KE data are available without severe restriction (which is indeed the case for the employed artificial data to build up our examples). However, in reality, it can be challenging to obtain sufficient quantified KE data, especially when measurements at multiple time points are needed, because of the potentially high costs and complexity of the experiments involved. Note that it is possible to perform KE mapping, i.e., mapping experimental data to precise KE measurements, while employing multiple data types within the same qAOP. A coherent KER mathematical formulation then allows these different data types to coexist within the same model. One important data type in this respect can be gene expression data, although it is not straightforward how to map such data to KEs. One approach to achieve this is by adoption of tools based on gene co-regulation analysis, which can map gene expression changes into KE changes. An example of this is the TXG-MAPr [50], mapping genes into coexpression-based cluster structures (i.e., modules), and subsequently quantifying their log₂-fold changes following exposure to relevant chemicals. Molecular AOPs are

another potentially useful approach meant to handle gene expression data, which measures KE activation using gene set enrichment analysis, entailing a link between KEs of AOP-Wiki [27] and molecular pathways from WikiPathways [51,52]. Other possible methods to quantify KEs include microscopic imaging, where time-lapse imaging can be employed to ‘easily’ obtain time course information that form a solid basis for mathematical modeling [53,54]. For instance, quantifying the amount of cell death can be done over time with Propidium iodide (PI) or Annexin V staining. As mentioned before, a lower availability of data, e.g., at only 1 or 2 time points, may preclude usage of our ODE-based qAOP. Nevertheless, such data may still allow for alternative approaches such as response–response or bayesian models, and can still be useful depending on the type of application.

A strength of our ODE-based qAOP mathematical framework lies in the natural extension that is possible to arrive at an AO formulation. Indeed, we showed how parameter variability across individuals can be linked to an AO distribution, thus using a deterministic model (based on an expected population average) to arrive at a distribution expected for an entire population of individuals potentially at risk. This implies that our proposed framework can fully describe variability amongst patients. When the underlying ODE system exhibits bistability, this would be able to partially explain the huge inter-individual variability that is typically expected at AO level. One could link the resulting AO score distributions to clinical data describing the severity of outcomes across a population of patients. This approach may involve correlating ODE model parameters with individual characteristics (e.g., age, gender, ethnicity, geographical location, lifestyle). By doing so, it could support decisions on optimal treatments for population subsets to avoid toxicity.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Filippo Di Tillio: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Joost B. Beltman:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Joost Beltman reports financial support was provided by Dutch Research Council. Joost Beltman reports financial support was provided by European Commission. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comtox.2024.100330>.

Data availability

Code to run the example qAOP models and to generate figures is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13898014>

qAOP example model data (Original data) (Zenodo)

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